

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT IPM MODULES ON STEM BORER *Chilo partellus* Swinhoe DEAD HEARTS, GRAIN AND FODDER YIELD OF KHARIF SORGHUM.Aher S.D.^{*1}, Iyas., M.D.^{*2}, Ambilwade P.P.^{*3}Timke S. H.^{*4}

1. Department of Agril. Entomology, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani-431402, India.
2. Department of Agril. Entomology, Sorghum Research Station, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani-431402, India.
3. Department of Agril. Entomology, Sorghum Research Station, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani-431402, India.
4. Department of Agril. Entomology, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani-431402, India.

sandipaaher7878@gmail.com

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Abstract

In Kharif 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 trial was conducted at Sorghum Research Station, VNMKV Parbhani (MS) India. In aspect of management of shoot pests of sorghum, Randomized Block Design (RBD) with seven treatments and three replications were demonstrated. In management of shoot pests different IPM components used for stem bore dead hearts at 45th DAE (Days After Emergence) significantly lowest per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₅ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (4.56%) which was at par with T₂ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (4.67%) in Kharif 2018-19 and 2019-20 (pooled data). In observation of grain and fodder, highest 29.08 and 69.39 q/ha yield was recorded in treatment T₅ (FA of Carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha + WA of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE). Highest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded in treatment T₅ [Furrow application of Carbofuran 3% G @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] 29.08 and 69.39 q/ha, while lowest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded 9.58 and 34.00 q/ha in Treatment T₇ Untreated control.

Key Ward- Bio-efficacy of Insecticides- Sorghum Pest- Sorghum Stem Borer.**Introduction**

Sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench] is an important cereal crop in India popularly known as 'Jowar' or 'Great millet'. It is originated in East Central Africa and it was acquainted with India from East Africa in the year, 1500 BC. Sorghum is nutritious its fodder contains in excess of 50 percent digestible nutrients with 8 percent protein, 2.5 percent fat and 45 percent nitrogen free concentrate. Maharashtra is major sorghum growing states in the country with an area, production, productivity of jowar was 2.23 Million ha, 1.61 Million tonnes and 720 kg ha⁻¹, respectively (Anonymous 2019). Several reasons have been attributed for the low grain and fodder yield of sorghum. Among them insect pests ravage is one of the principal factors. Insect pests continue to compete with humans for the sorghum crop and knowledge of both old and new pests has accumulated at a faster rate in recent years as the crop has received increasing attention. In Maharashtra about 18 important insect pests have been recorded on sorghum crop. Though many pests have been reported on sorghum crop in Maharashtra very few have economic status. The major being stem borer, *Chilo partellus* Swinhoe, sorghum shoot fly, *Atherigona soccata* Rondani, sorghum shoot bug, *Perigrinus maidis* Ashmead, earhead bug, *Calocoris angustatus* Lethir, army worm, *Mythimna separate* Walker, midge fly, *Contarinia sorghicola* Coquillette, sorghum aphid, *Melanaphis sacchari* Zehntner, earhead hairy caterpillar, *Euproctis subnotata* Walker and Ear head worm *Helicoverpa armigera* Hubner (Reddy and Davies, 1979).

The stem borer, *Chilo partellus* Swinhoe, attracted from one month and prior of seedling and placed white to creamy white eggs singly also in group on the surface of the leaves. The larva of stem borer after hatching, crawl to the plant stem and then make hole the stem and enter into stem and then feed inside the stem. As a result, central shoot become pale yellow and subsequently dead hearts forms. The tillers may be formed in about two-week-old seedlings but they may also get damaged. Loss due to *Chilo partellus* Swinhoe was observed even up to 88 per cent (Seshu Reddy, 1988).

Materials and Methods

Stem bore Dead heart count caused by stem borer was recorded from total plants at 45th days after emergence in each of the plot and replication and per cent dead heart was calculated using Abbott's (1925) formula:

$$\text{Dead hearts (\%)} = \frac{\text{No. of plants with dead hearts in a plot}}{\text{Total no. of plants in the plot}} \times 100.$$

Result and Discussion

In kharif season 2018-19, the per cent dead hearts of stem borer recorded between 4.28 to 18.04 on 45th days after emergence. Significantly lowest per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₅ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (4.28%) which was found statistically at par with treatment T₂ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed+ whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8kg /ha at 35 Days after emergence] (4.33%), T₆ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha+ spray of Novaluron 10 % at 35 Days after emergence] (7.31%) and T₄ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed+ *Bacillus thuringiensis* 20 ml/10 lit. of water at 35 Days after emergence] (8.70%). Next best treatment recorded T₃ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai /kg seed+ spray of Neem seed kernel extract 5% at 35 DAE] (11.17 %). Significantly highest per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₇ untreated control (18.04%) which was statistically at par with T₁ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed] (14.28%). While highest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded in treatment T₅ [Furrow application of Carbofuran 3% G @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] 27.81 and 66.33 q/ha, while lowest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded 10.80 and 34.00 q/ha in Treatment T₇ Untreated control.

In kharif 2019-20, the per cent dead hearts at 45th days after emergence ranged between 4.84 to 19.57 per cent. Significantly lowest per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₅ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (4.84%) which was at par with treatment T₂ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (5.01%). The next best treatment was T₄ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed+ *Bacillus thuringiensis* 20 ml/10 lit. of water at 35 Days after emergence] (7.18%). Significantly highest per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₇ untreated control

(19.57%) which was at par with T₁ [ST with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed] (13.51%). Maximum grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded in treatment T₅ [Furrow application of Carbofuran 3% G @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] 30.34 and 72.44 q/ha, while lowest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded 8.35 and 34.00 q/ha in Treatment T₇ Untreated control.

The pooled data on per cent dead hearts in *kharif* 2018-19 and 2019-20 recorded between 4.56 to 18.80 on 45th DAE. Significantly lowest per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₅ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha+ whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (4.56%) which was statistically at par with T₂ [Seed treatment with imidacloprid @ 3g ai/kg seed+ whorl application of carbofuron 3g @8kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (4.67%). The highest per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₇ untreated control (18.80%). Highest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded in treatment T₅ [Furrow application of Carbofuran 3% G @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] 29.08 and 69.39 q/ha, while lowest grain and fodder yield (q/ha) were recorded 9.58 and 34.00 q/ha in Treatment T₇ Untreated control.

Summery and Conclusion

Kharif-2018-19 significantly lowest per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₅ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha+ whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (4.28%). In *kharif*-2019-20 significantly lowest per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₅ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (4.84%).

Pooled studies indicated that in *kharif* 2018-19 and 2019-20 significantly lowest per cent of dead hearts were recorded in the treatment T₅ [Furrow application of carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha + whorl application of carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 Days after emergence] (4.56%).

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Table 1 Bio efficacy of different IPM components against stem borer of sorghum and their effect on grain and fodder yield in Kharif 2018.

Treatment No	Treatment Details	% SFDH at 28DAE	Grain yield (q/ha)	Fodder yield(q/ha)
1	ST with Imidacloprid @3gm ai/kg seed	13.67 (21.61)	16.51	41.61
2	ST with Imidacloprid@3g ai/kg seed + WA carbofuron 3g @ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE	12.17 (20.34)	28.69	68.37
3	ST with Imidacloprid @3gm ai/kg seed +Spray of NSKE 5% at 35 DAE	12.25 (20.40)	20.06	56.48
4	ST with Imidacloprid @ 3gm ai/kg seed + Bt.20 ml/10 lit. of water at 35DAE	10.03 (18.35)	22.05	62.56
5	FA of Carbofuron 3g@20 kg/ha +WA of carbofuron3g@ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE	9.65 (17.94)	27.81	66.33
6	FA of Carbofuron 3g@ 20 kg/ha + Spray of Novaluron10%at 35 DAE	13.76 (21.62)	23.57	65.95
7	UntreatedControl	47.40 (43.48)	10.80	34.00
	SE	2.39	2.69	6.13
	CD	5.26	5.92	13.50
	CV	12.5	15.42	13.29

Figures in parentheses are angular transformed value, SBDH=Stem Borer Dead Hearts, ST= Seed Treatment, FA= Farrow Applications, WA=Whorl application, DAE= Day after Emergence.

Table 2. Bio efficacy of different IPM components against stem borer of sorghum and their effect on grain and fodder yield in Kharif 2019.

Treatment No	Treatment Details	% SFDH at 28 DAE	Grain yield (q/ha)	Fodder yield (q/ha)
1	ST with Imidacloprid @3g ai./kg seed	9.17 (17.52)	15.60	40.27
2	STwithImidacloprid@3 g ai/kg seed + WA carbofuron 3g@ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE.	8.17 (16.4)	30.89	73.75
3	ST with Imidacloprid@3 g ai/kg seed + Spray of NSKE 5 % at 35 DAE	8.52 (16.62)	25.43	57.47
4	ST with Imidacloprid @3 g ai/kg seed+ Bt.20 ml/ 10lit. of water at 35 DAE	7.19 (15.09)	26.16	62.38
5	FA of Carbofuron 3g@20 kg/ha + WA of carbofuron3g@ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE	8.05 (16.02)	30.34	72.44
6	FA of Carbofuron 3g@ 20 kg/ha + Spray of Novaluron 10%at 35 DAE	9.54 (17.83)	24.77	65.95
7	UntreatedControl	25.52 (30.32)	8.35	34.00
	SE	2.29	2.83	6.50
	CD	5.04	6.23	14.30
	CV	15.13	15.01	13.70

Figures in parentheses are angular transformed value, SBDH=Stem Borer, ST= Seed Treatment, FA= Farrow Applications, WA=Whorl application, DAE= Day after Emergence.

Table 3. Bio efficacy of different IPM components against stem borer of sorghum and their effect on grain and fodder yield in *Kharif* 2018, 2019 and pooled data.

Treatment No	Treatment Details	% SFDH at 28DAE	Grain yield (q/ha)	Fodder yield (q/ha)
1	ST with Imidacloprid @3g ai/kg seed	11.42 (19.71)	16.05	40.94
2	ST with Imidacloprid@3gai/kg seed +WA carbofuron 3g@ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE	10.17 (18.48)	29.79	71.06
3	ST with Imidacloprid @3 g ai/kg seed + Spray of NSKE 5% at 35 DAE	10.38 (18.76)	22.75	56.98
4	STwith Imidacloprid @3g ai/kg seed+ Bt.20ml /10 lit. of water at 35 DAE	8.61 (16.91)	24.11	62.47
5	FA of Carbofuron 3g@20 kg/ha+WA of carbofuron 3g@ 8 kg/ha at 35 DAE	8.85 (17.04)	29.08	69.39
6	FA of Carbofuron 3g @ 20 kg/ha + Spray of Novaluron10% at 35 DAE.	11.65 (19.86)	24.17	65.96
7	Untreated Control	36.46 (37.12)	9.58	34.00
	SE	1.80	2.23	5.70
	CD	3.98	4.90	12.55
	CV	10.48	12.27	12.18

Figures in parentheses are angular transformed value, SBDH=Stem Borer Dead Hearts, ST= Seed Treatment, FA= Farrow Applications, WA=Whorl application, DAE= Day after Emergence